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International RN Training Courses: Overview

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The document provides an overview of altogether 49 radiological/nuclear-related (RN) training courses offered to the international community by 6 organisations: Seibersdorf CBRN Academy, Austria; Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE), Czech Republic; Hotzone Solutions Group, The Netherlands; Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A), Qatar; CBRN Academy, Sweden; International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Austria. Some of these organisations have cooperated in the design and conduct of these courses (e.g., Seibersdorf CBRN Academy and Hotzone Solutions Group).

The courses are analysed with regard to target audience, scope, objectives, and logistical details (e.g., course duration, didactics). They meet a wide range of learning objectives, such as: *Fundamentals of ionizing radiation; Biological and medical effects of radiation; Radiation detection; Radiation protection; Survey; Decontamination; Radiological and nuclear terrorism; Nuclear Emergencies; Tasks of the Incident Commander and Emergency Preparedness Coordinator; Response Processes and Capabilities.*

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ACRONYMS

CBR	Chemical-Biological-Radiological
CBRN	Chemical-Biological-Radiological-Nuclear
CBRNE	Chemical-Biological-Radiological-Nuclear-Explosive
CM	Crisis Management
EPDS	Emergency Personal Decontamination Station
EOD	Explosive Ordnance Disposal
HZS	Hotzone Solutions Group
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICS	Incident Command Systems
IED	Improvised Explosive Device
JCBRNDCOE	Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
Q-CBRN-A	Qatar CBRN Academy
RDD	Radiological Dispersal Devices
RN	Radiological and Nuclear
SCBA	Self-Contained Breathing Apparatus
SNM	Special Nuclear Material
WMD	Weapon of mass destruction

1 INTRODUCTION

This survey has identified the following 6 organisations conducting 49 RN-related training courses for the international community of first responders:¹

1. Seibersdorf CBRN Academy, Austria: 10 courses
2. Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE), Czech Republic: 4 courses
3. International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Austria: 8 courses
4. Hotzone Solutions Group, The Netherlands: 19 courses
5. Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A), Qatar: 7 courses
6. CBRN Academy, Sweden: 1 course.

This document profiles these organisations and provides an overview for each RN-related training course with regard to course type, duration, target audience, content, learning objectives, training method and logistical details.²

¹ Status: 15 December 2020

² This document is regarded as a “Living Document”, i.e., its content will be updated in the course of the INCLUDING project.

2 INTERNATIONAL RN TRAINING COURSES

The international community differentiates between radiological terrorism (RT) and nuclear terrorism (NT). NT involves weapons of mass destruction; RT deploys weapons of mass disruption. In either case, a non-state actor needs to acquire nuclear or other radioactive materials to use in a crime or carry out an act of terrorism.

RT is more likely to occur, since the number of radiation sources used globally in industry, medicine, agriculture and research amounts to tens of thousands such sources. Worldwide, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) has tabulated more than 20,000 operators of significant radioactive sources: more than 10,000 radiotherapy units for medical care are in use; about 12,000 industrial sources for radiography are supplied annually; and about 300 irradiator facilities, containing radioactive sources for industrial applications, are in operation. However, the IAEA has also identified over 100 countries providing inadequate control over some of these radiation sources.³

The consequences of a radiological threat are either intentional, uncontrolled dispersion of radioactive material (e.g., explosion of a radiological dispersal device (RDD)), that can result in contaminated individuals and /or the near-by environment, or deliberate, uncontrolled irradiation of individuals by a radiation source (radiological exposure device (RED)).

NT requires access to suitable nuclear material⁴. Such material is stored and handled at several hundred dedicated civilian and military installations worldwide, each facility subject to high standards of physical security. The consequences of NT are significantly more severe than those of RT, i.e., a nuclear explosion will result in severe physical destruction of buildings and infrastructure, wide-spread environmental contamination, and a large number of radioactively contaminated victims, partially with severe burn wounds. The probability for an NT event to happen is significantly lower than that for an RT event due to the high level of security at nuclear facilities storing and handling such material and the special know-how and infrastructure needed by the criminal.

In response to the RT and NT threats some countries have taken the initiative to offer to the international community dedicated training courses. The following section summarizes as examples for such efforts the content of RT- and NT-related training courses offered by Austria, Czech Republic, The Netherlands, Qatar, Sweden, and the IAEA.

2.1 Seibersdorf CBRN Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories, Austria

Seibersdorf CBRN Academy, in partnership with *CBRN Protection* and *Hotzone Solution Middle East*, provides realistic CBRNE Training for emergency responders and military personnel. This cooperation combines operational experience with more than 50 years of activity in radiation protection training. Training is designed to ensure that emergency response personnel gets an in-depth understanding of the specific hazards, risks, and response mechanisms associated with CBRNE emergencies and incidents.⁵

³ <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/pressreleases/inadequate-control-worlds-radioactive-sources>

⁴ Special Nuclear Material (SNM). For an official definition look at Art.1, point 2 of the “INTERNATIONAL CONVENTION FOR THE SUPPRESSION OF ACTS OF NUCLEAR TERRORISM”, UN 2005.

⁵ **Note:** CBRN training courses offered address – besides R and N issues – also C and B-related topics; these topics are not covered in this report.

A special feature is the use of sealed (closed) and unsealed (open) radioactive sources, always placing special focus on the safety of training participants. When they are confronted with scenarios involving dirty bombs or nuclear emergencies, among others, knowing how to deal with unsealed radioactive substances is of vital importance for emergency response services and military personnel.

The following radiation sources are used in the training courses: Cobalt-60, Technetium-99m, Cesium-137, Fluorine-18, Americium-241/Beryllium.

The Seibersdorf CBRN Academy offers the following 10 training courses:

INDIVIDUAL LEVEL

- RAD Basic Course
- Basic CBRN Course
- CBRN Medical Responder Course
- Nuclear Emergency Preparedness Course

GROUP LEVEL

- Radiation Emergency Response Course
- CBRN Incident Response Course
- Nuclear Emergency Response Course
- Radiation Decontamination Course

COMMAND LEVEL

- Radiation Incident Commander Course
- CBRNE (CBRN EOD) Incident Commander Course.

No.	1
Title of training course	RAD Basic Course
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	60 hours (min. 8 days)
Course content	The basics of radiation will be taught in a classroom-setting and trained practically, with different radioisotopes. The course will be of a duration of two weeks (recommended). Week one will have its focus on the basic radiation knowledge and understanding, including the handling of detection devices. Week two will be scenario-based training.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basics in radiation protection • Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources • Be familiar with the use of detection equipment • Be familiar with orphan and misused sources • Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment in a live environment • Understand and be able to apply safe work practices.
Training method	Classroom and practical training

Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/rad-basic-course
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No.	2
Title of training course	Basic CBRN Course – Individual Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	16
Course duration	100 hours (min. 12 days)
Course content	The basics of CBRN materials will be taught in a classroom-setting and trained practically, with different chemicals, radioisotopes and biological simulants. The participants will learn the effects of RN materials and the measures they can take to protect themselves against them. The course will be of a duration of three weeks (recommended). Week one will have its focus on the basics of radioactivity, week two deals with Chemical Warfare Agents and toxic industrial chemicals and the last week gives participants an overview on biological agents.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview on properties of CBRN materials • Familiarization with protective measures and equipment • Recognize signs and symptoms of exposure to CBRN agents • Familiarization with detection of CBRN materials • Familiarization with the various CBRN decontamination processes.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/cbrn-basic-course

No.	3
Title of training course	CBRN Medical Responder Course – Individual Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	40 hours (min. 5 days)
Course content	This course provides participants with the knowledge, skills and abilities to analyze the medical risks at a hazardous materials or weapons of mass destruction incident; and to plan and implement procedures to respond to potential health impacts on response personnel in a pre-hospital setting. The main method is individual and sub-team training. The course is based on the competencies of emergency medical services (EMS) personnel, as outlined in NFPA 473, Standard for Competence of EMS Personnel to a Hazardous Materials/Weapons of Mass Destruction Incidents, and provides EMS personnel with the core competencies of operations level responders as defined in Chapter 5 of NFPA 472, Standard

	<p>for Competence of Responders to Hazardous Materials/Weapons of Mass Destruction Incidents.</p> <p>Learning is provided through theoretical lessons, followed by guided and supervised, team-based practical exercises using chemical and biological simulants and radioactive materials.</p> <p>The course consists of theoretical and practical elements, including the use of sealed and unsealed radioactive sources (types of radiation: alpha/beta/gamma).</p> <p>The course will be one week-long (recommended). The practical exercises will be a realistic (use of radioisotopes and simulants) scenario-based training.</p>
Learning objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Analysis a chemical agent incident to determine the magnitude of the problem in terms of outcome by the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Knowledge on chemical and physical properties of CBRN; ○ Identification of signs and symptoms of exposure to CBRN, mainly chemical agent; ○ Prediction of the potential behavior of CBRN agents; 2. Planning the response by identifying <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the relevant equipment to support Hot Zone entries; ○ health hazards and risks associated with Hot Zone activities; ○ standard and non-standard decontamination materials and discuss their advantages and disadvantages; control zones; ○ the equipment and resources for a medical monitoring station; ○ necessary communication with other on scene personnel; 3. Planning a response to a medical emergency. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Implement the Planned Response by obtaining hazard and toxicity information, ○ decon methods, ○ establishing a medical monitoring station, ○ conducting pre-entry and post-entry medical monitoring of personnel involved in toxic entries and keeping records and responding to emergencies.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/medical-responder-course

No.	4
Title of training course	Nuclear Emergency Preparedness Course – Individual Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	

Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	60 hours (min. 8 days)
Course content	<p>The scope of this course is to familiarize participants with the various elements of Nuclear Emergencies, having its cause in accidents at Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) or incidents involving Special Nuclear Material (SNM). The course will be held in the Seibersdorf Academy and at the NPP Zwentendorf in Austria. The course consists of theoretical and practical elements, including the use of sealed and unsealed radioactive sources (including 4 types of radiation – alpha, beta, gamma, neutrons). The participants will be introduced to sampling of radioactive material, cordoning tasks and how to set up radiation check points. 2 days of this course will be run at a non-functional NPP which allows for unlimited and safe access to all elements of the nuclear energy production cycle. The course will be two weeks long (recommended). Week one will focus on the basics of nuclear energy. Week two will be scenario-based training, including two days at the NPP Zwentendorf.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basics of NPPs • Be familiar with Special Nuclear Material • Have an overview on how to prepare for nuclear emergencies • Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources • Be familiar with the use of detection equipment • Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment in a live environment • Understand and be able to apply safe work practices with radioisotopes
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/nuclear-emergency-preparedness-course

No.	5
Title of training course	Radiation Emergency Response Course – Group Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	60 hours (min. 8 days)
Course content	<p>The scope of this course is to familiarize participants with the response to Radiation Emergencies, originating from either radiation accidents, orphan sources, illicit trafficking or the malicious use of radioactive material.</p> <p>The participants will be introduced to the response to emergencies involving radioactive material.</p> <p>The course consists of theoretical and practical elements, including the use of sealed and unsealed radioactive sources (types of radiation: alpha/beta/gamma).</p> <p>The course will be two weeks long (recommended). Week one will focus on the basics and different kinds of radiation emergencies and the</p>

	response mechanism. Week two will be realistic (use of radioisotopes) scenario-based training.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basics of Radiation Emergencies • Understand the malicious use of radioactive material • Gain confidence in how to respond to radiological incidents • Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources • Be familiar with the use of detection equipment • Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment in a live environment • Understand and be able to apply safe work practices.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/rad-emergency-response-course

No.	6
Title of training course	CBRN Incident Response Course – Group Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	40 hours (min. 5 days)
Course content	<p>The scope of this course is to provide first responders and military personnel with the required competence to respond to incidents involving CBRN materials and CBRNE devices, and assess the risks posed by these materials.</p> <p>The course will be held in the Seibersdorf Academy in Austria. The main method is sub-team training.</p> <p>The participants will be introduced to the response to emergencies involving CBRN materials.</p> <p>Learning is provided through theoretical lessons, followed by guided and supervised, team-based practical exercises using chemical and biological simulants and radioactive materials.</p> <p>The course consists of theoretical and practical elements, including the use of sealed and unsealed radioactive sources (types of radiation: alpha/beta/gamma).</p> <p>The course will be one week-long (recommended). The practical training will be a realistic (use of radioisotopes and simulants) scenario-based training.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The properties and effects of CWA, TIMs, biological and radiological agents • Categories of CBRNE Devices (CBRN IEDs, CBRN DDs & CBRN SDs) • The handling of dangerous materials • Toxicology (first effects) • Terrorist action using CBR materials • Team protection procedures (IPE, donning/doffing, avoidance of contamination) • Theory of decontamination and application of selected decontamination procedures (e.g. immediate decontamination of CBRN and EOD/Bomb Technician personnel and equipment or eventually provide an isolation of suspected contaminated assets)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The setup of an Emergency Personal Decontamination Station (EPDS). • Management of a contaminated operator • Definition and marking of an initial hazardous CBR area • CBR hazard area, pre and post blast • CBR hazard assessment techniques, pre and post blast, including x-ray • CBR detection employing available equipment as user, pre and post blast • Protection of forensic evidence pre and post blast • Collection of pre and post blast information and evidence • Provision of specialist CBRN EOD technical advice for a higher command • Coordination with CBRN specialists in a CBRN/EOD incident • Definition of the potential outcome of a CBRN device.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/cbrne-incident-response-course

No.	7
Title of training course	Nuclear Emergency Response Course – Group Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	60 hours (min. 8 days)
Course content	<p>The scope of this course is to train the participants in the response to Nuclear Emergencies, having its cause in accidents at Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) or incidents involving Special Nuclear Material (SNM).</p> <p>The course will be held in the Seibersdorf Academy and at the NPP Zwentendorf in Austria. The course consists of theoretical and practical elements, including the use of sealed and unsealed radioactive sources (4 types of radiation, alpha/beta/gamma/neutrons).</p> <p>The participants will be introduced to the response to nuclear emergencies. Up to 5 days of this course will be run at a non-functional NPP which allows for unlimited and safe access to all elements of the nuclear energy production cycle.</p> <p>The course will be two weeks long (recommended). Week one will focus on the basics of nuclear emergencies and the response mechanism. Week two will be scenario-based training at the NPP Zwentendorf.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basics of NPPs • Be familiar with SNMs • Learn how to respond to nuclear incidents • Understand how to support the incident commander • Gain confidence in responding to incidents with open radioactive sources • Be familiar with the use of detection equipment • Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment in a live environment • Understand and be able to apply safe work practices.

Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/nuclear-emergency-response-course

No.	8
Title of training course	Radiation Decontamination Course – Group Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	40 hours (min. 5 days)
Course content	<p>The scope of this course is to familiarize participants with the principles of decontamination in case of radiological incidents, under the safe use of unsealed radioactive emitters.</p> <p>The course will be held in the Seibersdorf Academy in Austria. The participants will practically decontaminate variously sized items, by performing operational and thorough decontamination exercises.</p> <p>The course consists of theoretical and practical elements, with its focus on performing realistic decontamination operations.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the principles of radioactive contamination and decontamination • Be familiar with open radioactive sources • Gain confidence in how to safely and efficiently decontaminate equipment, vehicles and personnel • Understand how to handle radioactive waste • Be familiar with the use of detection equipment • Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment in a live environment • Understand and be able to apply safe work practices.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-academy-seibersdorf/rad-decontamination-course

No.	9
Title of training course	Radiation Incident Commander Course – Command Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	12
Course duration	60 hours (min. 8 days)
Course content	The scope of this course is to train the participants in management of radiological Emergencies, originating from either nuclear incidents (NPP/

	<p>IND), orphan sources or misuse/illicit trafficking. The participants will also learn consequence management and the basics in warning and reporting.</p> <p>The course will be held at the Seibersdorf Academy in Austria. The aim of the course is to train the participant to be able to support or to act as the incident commander. This course consists of theory and practical work, including the use of radioactive sources (types of radiation: alpha/bet/gamma/neutrons).</p> <p>The course will be of a duration of two weeks (recommended), where week 1 will have its focus on the basics of the incident commanders work. Week two will be realistic scenario-based training, paired with case studies.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the basics of the incident commanders' tasks and responsibilities • Be familiar with different radiological incidents • Learn how to handle radiological incidents • Learn how to support/ be the incident commander • Learn the basics of the warning and reporting system according to ATP45 • Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources • Be familiar with the use of detection equipment • Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment in a live environment • Understand and be able to apply safe work practices
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/rad-incident-commander-course

No.	10
Title of training course	CBRNE (CBRN EOD) Incident Commander Course – Command Level
Organizer	Seibersdorf Academy, Seibersdorf Laboratories
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international, NATO)	International
Target audience	First responders and military personnel
Max. attendance	16
Course duration	80 hours (min. 10 days)
Course content	<p>The scope of this advanced course is to train the participants in commanding CBRNE response efforts at a CBRNE incident.</p> <p>The course will be held at the Seibersdorf Academy in Austria.</p> <p>At the end of this course the CBRNE Incident Commander should be able to perform the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse a CBRN EOD Incident; • Plan response ops; • Implement a response to change the outcome consistent with emergency response plan or SOP; • Evaluate the progress of the planned response; • Terminate the emergency phase of the incident; • To act within the applicable legal and safety regulations.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be familiar with CBRNE Agents and Personal Protection Equipment • Recognize Chemical Agents of Opportunity for Terrorism,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the Incident Command Systems (ICS), • Be able to draft Pre-Incident Plans and Procedures, • Understand Incident Management Software Programs, • Be familiar with the principles of Stand-by/Recall of Emergency Response Personnel, • Understand Expedient Chemical/Biological Release Mitigation Methods, • Be familiar with the procedures for prolonged SCBA/PPE Operations, • Understand Manpower Rehabilitation and Replacement Logistics for Sustained Ops • Understand Stress Management for Emergency Personnel, • Be familiar with Mass Decontamination, • Have an Overview on Human Behavior during a CBRN crisis, • Understand the use of aviation assets, • Be familiar with the Security of Critical Facilities, • Be familiar with Medical Emergency Operations Plans, • Understand Multiple Agency Communication, • Understand the Criminal Investigation of Deliberate CBRNE Events, • Be able to plan Long Term Response and Recovery, • Recognize Environmental Concerns, • Have an overview on Emerging/Next Generation Response Technologies • Be familiar with Case Studies.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.seibersdorf-laboratories.at/en/products/international-training-program/cbrn-training/cbrne-incident-commander-course

2.2 Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE), Czech Republic

Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE) is a NATO military body and multi-nationally sponsored organization which offers its expertise and experience to the benefit of the NATO Alliance and other partners. Its RN-related activities are focused on:

- Support of CBRN Defence Education, Training and Exercises
- Experimentation support
- CBRN Lesson Learned, Evaluation and Analysis
- CBRN Modelling and Simulation
- COE organized Courses, Workshops and Conferences
- Support others COEs and mutual cooperation among COEs.

JCBRNDCOE offers the following 4 RN courses:

- International Radiological Assistance Program Training for Emergency Response (I-RAPTER) Basic Course;
- International Radiological and Nuclear Training for Emergency Response (I-RAD) Basic Course;

- Introduction to the International CBRN Training Curriculum for Trainers of First Responders to CBRN Incidents Course 2020;
- Consequence Management After a CBRN Incident Course.

No.	11
Title of training course	International Radiological Assistance Program Training for Emergency Response (I-RAPTER) Basic Course
Organizer	Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE)
Country	Czech Republic
Co-organizer(s)	US Department of Energy (DOE); US DOE National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA)
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Emergency response personnel (radiation protection specialists, first responders, law enforcement, and emergency managers) with minimal training in radiological emergency response or experienced professionals seeking refresher training.
Max. attendance	30
Course duration	5 days
Course content	The course covers response methods to a variety of nuclear and radiological incidents, including search, response to a portal alarm, consequence management in the event of a release of radiological material, and addresses events ranging from a small, localized release to a larger incident, such as a radiological dispersal device.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the principles needed to organize and conduct a radiological emergency response • Have practical experience applying those principles in realistic scenarios and • Understand how to protect themselves and the public from contamination.
Training method	Briefings, equipment demonstrations and field exercises employing a wide variety of radiation detection instrumentation, radiation sources, and personal protective equipment.
Weblink	https://www.jcbrncoe.cz/tp/course/index.php?categoryid=27

No.	12
Title of training course	International Radiological and Nuclear Training for Emergency Response (I-RAD) Basic Course
Organizer	Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE)
Country	Czech Republic
Co-organizer(s)	CBRN Defence Centre, Korneuburg, Austria; US Department of Energy (DOE); US DOE National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA)
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	This course is designed for emergency response personnel (radiation protection specialists, first responders, law enforcement, and emergency managers) with basic training in radiological emergency response and/or experienced professionals seeking refresher training.
Max. attendance	30
Course duration	5 days

Course content	The course covers response methods to a variety of nuclear and radiological incidents, including search, response to a portal alarm, consequence management in the event of a release of radiological material, and addresses events ranging from a small, localized release to a larger incident, such as a radiological dispersal device.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the principles needed to organize and conduct a radiological emergency response, • Have practical experience applying those principles in realistic scenarios and • Understand how to protect themselves and the public from contamination.
Training method	Briefings, equipment demonstrations and field exercises employing a wide variety of radiation detection instrumentation, radiation sources, and personal protective equipment.
Weblink	https://www.jcbrncoe.cz/tp/course/index.php?categoryid=33

No.	13
Title of training course	Introduction to the International CBRN Training Curriculum for Trainers of First Responders to CBRN Incidents Course 2020
Organizer	Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE)
Country	Czech Republic
Co-organizer(s)	US Department of Energy (DOE); US DOE National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA); Civil Emergency Planning Committee (CEPC)
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	CBRN trainers with substantial experience in fire and rescue, police or paramedic services, or similar activities (civilian and military) and with training activities in this field. It is expected that attendees will have experience in delivering CBRN training to first responders and have good English language skills.
Max. attendance	18
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	The aim of this course is to familiarize the course participants with the Introduction to the International CBRN Training Curriculum for Trainers of First Responders; to provide knowledge and understanding required for the implementation of the Introduction to the International CBRN Training Curriculum for Trainers of First Responders within their own nations, and to enhance interoperability among first responders in an international response to CBRN events. This course is organised in close cooperation with the Civil Emergency Planning Committee (CEPC).
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the security context behind national and international CBRN preparedness and response; • Understand the methods employed to recognise a CBRN incident; • Understand the protection of responders and safety of victims; • Understand the decontamination options at a CBRN incident; • Understand basic medical and psychological considerations in relation to CBRN incidents; • Understand the basic principles of detection and sample taking; • Understand the principles of command and control in relation to CBRN incidents; • Understand the implications of bilateral or international assistance for local first responders.
Training method	Briefings, equipment demonstrations

Weblink	https://www.jcbrncoe.cz/tp/course/index.php?categoryid=33
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No.	14
Title of training course	Consequence Management After a CBRN Incident Course
Organizer	Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE)
Country	Czech Republic
Co-organizer(s)	CBRN Defence Centre, Korneuburg, Austria; US Department of Energy (DOE); US DOE National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA)
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course is developed for key elements of consequence management structures including the police, firefighters, health services, hospitals, military, civil defence (if applicable), emergency management authorities, public information, specialist teams, such as counterterrorism units or investigation.
Max. attendance	30
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	The aim is to introduce and describe CBRN Consequence Management, NATO Crisis Management concept, organisation, systems and procedures including Cooperation and Partnership initiatives in CBRN Crisis / Consequence Management to NATO and Partner Nation officers and their civilian equivalents.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify principal NATO and EU CM bodies, systems and procedures, and explain the NATO and EU CM process; • Explain CM after CHEM incident; • Explain CM after BIO incident; • Explain CM after RAD/NUC incident; • Explain Lessons Learned from recent NATO and EU commitments and exercises; identify the importance of Rules of Engagement, Process and Public Information during the planning and implementation of Crisis Response Operations.
Training method	Briefings.
Weblink	https://www.jcbrncoe.cz/tp/course/index.php?categoryid=33

2.3 International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Austria

The IAEA offers a range of training courses covering nuclear and radiological emergency preparedness and response. Training is offered in different formats, including classroom workshops, practical sessions, exercises, virtual reality and webinars.

IAEA offers the following 8 RN courses listed below:

- Evaluating Preparedness for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency;
- First Response to a Radiological Emergency;
- Preparedness and Response for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency;
- Medical Response to a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency;
- Preparedness and Response for an Emergency at a Research Reactor;
- Protecting the Public During a Nuclear Power Reactor Emergency;

- Communication with the Public in a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency;
- Workshop on Arrangements for the Termination of a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency.

No.	15
Title of training course	Evaluating Preparedness for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The five-day course targets emergency preparedness coordinators who have a key role in the organization of exercises. These include: technical and scientific support personnel who lead the development of exercise scenarios and simulated radiological data; emergency planners, and training specialists.
Max. attendance	
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	The course, based on the Preparation, Conduct and Evaluation of Exercises to Test Preparedness for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency (EPR-EXERCISE, 2005) , presents concepts, terminology and introduces a process for the preparation, conduct and evaluation of an exercise. The course covers the general concepts of exercises; the preparation process and exercise manual; exercise objectives; scenario, injects and data; radiological data for exercises, and exercise evaluation.
Learning objectives	Assist states in managing exercises by testing preparedness for nuclear or radiological emergencies.
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/evaluating-preparedness-for-a-nuclear-or-radiological-emergency

No.	16
Title of training course	First Response to a Radiological Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course targets first responders to a radiological emergency, such as: law enforcement teams; fire brigades; emergency medical services; public information officers; resource coordinators; first responder monitors; forensic evidence management teams; national officials; and emergency services personnel and managers
Max. attendance	
Course duration	4 days
Course aim & content	This programme offers training on the concepts and operational response steps recommended for first responders. The course is based on a task-based manual and provides guidance on first response organisation functions, for example: assessment of radiological hazard and establishment of an inner cordoned area; exposure pathways and protective actions; field triage for mass casualties

	events; monitoring and decontamination of the public, responders, vehicles and equipment.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain assessment of radiological hazard and establishment of an inner cordoned area; • Explain exposure pathways and protective actions; • Explain field triage for mass casualty events; • Explain monitoring and decontamination of the public, responders, vehicles and equipment
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/first-response-to-a-radiological-emergency

No.	17
Title of training course	Preparedness and Response for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	DOE/USA and NNSA
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course targets professionals responsible for preparing for and responding to a nuclear or radiological emergency at the national, regional, local or facility levels.
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	<p>This training course helps Member States implement the IAEA Safety Standard Preparedness and Response for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency (GSR Part 7) in their national emergency preparedness and response frameworks. It also reviews changes made to the document in November 2015. The programme includes discussions on potential implementation challenges and areas that could require further guidance and support. The following topic areas are addressed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Basic radiation concepts and biological effects; ○ Principles of radiation detection, ○ Radiological search operations and mission planning; ○ Personal protective equipment, ○ Radioactive material identification and Characterization, ○ Radiation contamination and source recovery; ○ Generic criteria for use in preparedness for and response to a radiation emergency; ○ Response and assistance network; ○ Incident and emergency communication; ○ IAEA roles and responsibilities in preparedness for and to radiation emergencies; ○ IAEA education and training in emergency preparedness and response. <p>Based on a task-based manual, it provides guidance on first response organisation functions, for example: assessment of radiological hazard and establishment of an inner cordoned area; exposure pathways and protective actions; field triage for mass casualties events; monitoring and decontamination of the public, responders, vehicles and equipment.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dosimetric criteria (generic criteria and reference levels); • Emergency planning zones and distances; • Hazard assessment and categories;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of emergency workers; • Protection strategies; • Termination of a nuclear or radiological emergency • Training on the concepts and operational response steps recommended for first responders.
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/preparedness-and-response-for-a-nuclear-or-radiological-emergency

No.	18
Title of training course	Medical Response to a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	<p>The course targets professionals involved in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • response at the scene, including medical first responders, emergency medical technicians, ambulance attendants and other medical personnel who may be called to respond to a radiological emergency or emergencies at nuclear facilities; • response at the hospital, including emergency physicians, nursing staff, support staff and medical administrators who may be called upon to manage critical care for overexposed, contaminated or potentially contaminated patients; • advanced medical care, including medical specialists who manage the care for severely exposed or internally contaminated patients.
Max. attendance	
Course duration	9 days
Course aim & content	<p>This training course helps countries strengthen their preparedness to respond to emergencies involving radiation. It is based on the publication Generic Procedures for Medical Response during a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency (EPR- MEDICAL 2005) and other publications co-sponsored by the IAEA and World Health Organization.</p> <p>The programme comprises three modules that provide guidance on early diagnosis, general management, treatment and other elements related to the organisation of the medical response.</p>
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responding first at the scene, managing overexposed or contaminated patients; • Protecting responders; • Transferring patients; • Setting up the emergency area; • Diagnosis and radiological considerations and advanced techniques and methods to diagnose, assess and treat overexposed individuals
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/medical-response-to-a-nuclear-or-radiological-emergency

No.	19
Title of training course	Preparedness and Response for an Emergency at a Research Reactor
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course targets local and facility emergency planners, emergency response coordinators and emergency managers.
Max. attendance	
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	This training course assists Member States in preparations for an effective response to a research reactor emergency in line with the Generic Procedures for Response to a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency at Research Reactors (EPR-RESEARCH REACTOR, 2011) . The five-day programme focuses on action guides for the facility emergency response team, instructions, practical procedures, and tools that can be adapted by a Member State to build a basic capability to respond to a research reactor emergency.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing procedures for on-site and off-site protective actions; • Establishing response teams, including structuring roles and responsibilities; • Organising emergency response actions at a reactor site; and • Reviewing the threat category of a research reactor site.
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/preparedness-and-response-for-an-emergency-at-a-research-reactor

No.	20
Title of training course	Protecting the Public During a Nuclear Power Reactor Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course targets decision-makers, local and facility emergency planners, emergency response coordinators and emergency managers in a nuclear or radiological emergency, including public information officers and emergency preparedness and response experts at local and national levels.
Max. attendance	
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	This training course strengthens Member States' capacity to make effective decisions regarding public protective actions in the event of an emergency involving actual or projected severe fuel damage in a light water reactor or spent fuel pool. It is based on the IAEA publication Actions to Protect the Public in an Emergency due to Severe Conditions at a Light Water Reactor (EPR-NPP PPA 2013) . The five-day programme focuses on how to make decisions to protect

	the public, using nuclear power plant conditions and environmental measurements made after a release of radioactive material as a basis. It also looks at ways to help the public understand the radiological health hazard.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase national capability to protect members of the public in case of an accidental release at a NPP • Improve public understanding of radiation-risk related issues.
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/protecting-the-public-during-a-nuclear-power-reactor-emergency

No.	21
Title of training course	Communication with the Public in a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course targets those responsible for communicating with the public and the media, as well as those in charge of coordinating official information in a nuclear or radiological emergency, including public information officers and emergency preparedness and response experts at local and national levels.
Max. attendance	
Course duration	5 days
Course aim & content	The course, based on Communication with the Public in a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency (EPR-Public Communications, 2012) highlights communication principles and tools that assist public information officers in preparing for communication that helps mitigate the emergency's effects. The programme covers topics including the preparation of a public communication programme with a strategy that is tailored to relevant scenarios and key audiences. The course uses lessons learned from past emergencies, simulated scenarios and exercises. It also highlights best practices.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening Member States' capacity to communicate effectively with the public in a nuclear or radiological emergency • Teach basic issues related to risk perception, media relations and spokesperson selection.
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/communication-with-the-public-in-a-nuclear-or-radiological-emergency

No.	22
Title of training course	Workshop on Arrangements for the Termination of a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency
Organizer	International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
Country	Austria
Co-organizer(s)	

Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	The course targets professionals working in preparedness for and response to nuclear or radiological emergencies at the national, regional, local or facility levels
Max. attendance	
Course duration	4 days
Course aim & content	This training course helps Member States to develop and implement arrangements for the termination of a nuclear or radiological emergency, as required by the IAEA Safety Standard Preparedness and Response for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency (GSR Part 7) and the Safety Guide on Arrangements for the Termination of a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency (GSG-11) . It highlights the procedures for adapting and lifting protective actions; medical follow-up and provision of mental health and psychosocial support; infrastructural elements necessary to support adequate capability for response during the transition phase, and the facilitation of smooth and prompt resumption of social and economic activity.
Learning objectives	Focus on the necessary steps to declare the formal end to a nuclear or radiological emergency.
Training method	Classroom workshops
Weblink	https://www.iaea.org/services/education-and-training/training-courses/epr/workshop-on-arrangements-for-the-termination-of-a-nuclear-or-radiological-emergency

2.4 HotZone Solutions Group, The Netherlands

Hotzone Solutions Group (HZS) is an independent company, providing a wide range of training, equipment, security and consulting services to the chemical, biological, radiological/ nuclear and explosives (CBRNE) response and environmental protection community.

The corporate headquarters is based in the Netherlands and HZS maintains regional offices in Belgium, Brazil and the United Arab Emirates. The company was established in 2009 with field experience in CBRNE defence, international weapons inspection, emergency response, environmental protection and counterterrorism.⁶

HZS mission is to enable first responders to prevent, prepare for, respond to, and recover from the full spectrum of CBRNE threats. These threats include industrial accidents, acts of domestic and international terrorism, involving chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear, and explosive (CBRNE) materials.

HZS training is structured to cater to five different levels of responders:

- Individual (Awareness);
- Individual (Advanced);
- Collective (Response Team Member);
- Collective (Response Team Leader);
- Command;
- e-Learning.

⁶ <https://hotzonesolutions.org/about-us/>

HZS Individual (Awareness) Level courses balance practical and theoretical based training. Beyond this, training at the Individual (Advanced) Level can be focused on specific/tailored requirements up to and including work with live chemical agents, biological and radioactive materials. The Individual Level courses offered by HZS are listed below:

INDIVIDUAL – AWARENESS LEVEL

- CBRN General Awareness Training
- Radiation Safety Awareness
- CBRNE Detection
- CBRN Decontamination
- CBRN Medical

INDIVIDUAL – ADVANCED LEVEL

- Live Agent Training Radiological Individual Level
- Live Agent CBRN Medical Responder
- CBRN Forensics

HZS Collective Level courses focus on specific/tailored requirements up to and including work with live chemical agents, biological and radioactive materials. HZS offers several Collective Level courses listed below:

COLLECTIVE – RESPONSE TEAM MEMBER LEVEL

- Live Agent CBR Response Team Member
- Nuclear Emergency Training (NET)
- Sampling and Identification of Biological, Chemical and Radiological Agents (SIBCRA)
- Live Agent Sampling and Identification of Biological, Chemical and Radiological Agents (SIBCRA)
- Live Agent CBR Device Investigation

COLLECTIVE – RESPONSE TEAM LEADER LEVEL

- Live Agent CBR Response Team Leader

In addition, HZS offers the following *Command Level courses*:

COMMAND LEVEL

- CBRN EOD Incident Commander
- CBRNE Airport/Border Crossing Security
- CBRNE Special Event Planning and Management
- CBRNE Threat and Vulnerability Assessments

– Planning a Response to a CBRNE EOD Incident

No.	23
Title of training course	CBRN General Awareness Training – Individual Level Awareness
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	Classroom capacity
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This classroom course familiarises participants with CBRN materials and their respective properties and the measures they can take to protect themselves against them.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Properties of CBRN materials • Protective measures and equipment • Signs and symptoms of exposure to CBRN agents • Detection of CBRN materials • Decontamination processes
Training method	Classroom training only
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	24
Title of training course	Radiation Safety Awareness – Individual Level Awareness
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	Classroom capacity
Course duration	4 days (30 hours)
Course aim & content	This classroom course familiarises participants with the different types of radiation, detection principles, and protective measures.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Types of radiation • Detection technologies • Protective measures • Protective equipment • Decontamination principles
Training method	Classroom training only
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	25
Title of training course	CBRN Detection – Individual Level Awareness
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)	

Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	Classroom capacity
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This course covers detection technologies and systems associated with chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear and explosive agents.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current detection capabilities and limitations • Types of chemical agent detection instruments • Biological agent detection instruments and processes • Radiological agent detection instruments • Explosive detection instruments and processes • Emerging detection technologies • Detection exercises with simulants (where applicable)
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	26
Title of training course	CBRN Decontamination – Individual Level Awareness
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	Classroom capacity
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This course covers decontamination systems and technologies associated with chemical, biological and radiological agents.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current decontamination capabilities • Chemical agent decontamination technologies and limitations • Biological agent decontamination technologies and processes • Radiological agent decontamination technologies, process, residual contamination control • Emerging technologies
Training method	Classroom training only
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	27
Title of training course	CBRN Medical – Individual Level Awareness
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Medical responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	3 days (24 hours)
Course aim & content	This course familiarises participants with medical countermeasures in case of exposure to CBRN materials.

Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognising a CBRN event based on visible signs and symptoms • Toxicology of CBRN materials • Safety within the Hot Zone • Working as a first responder in a Hot Zone (selection and use of protective equipment) • Dealing with CBRN casualties inside and outside the Hot Zone • Emergency decontamination (materials and procedures)
Training method	Classroom training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	28
Title of training course	Live Agent Training Radiological – Individual Level Advanced
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	Seibersdorf Academy, Austria
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This course enables participants to (a) detect radiological agents, (b) protect humans and critical infrastructure from radiation emitting sources, and (c) implement appropriate health and safety measures.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical principles of detection and protection • Establishing safety zones and safe distances • Use of protective equipment (personal and collective) • Personal dosimetry • Record keeping of exposure • Provision of advice to local authorities • National and international rules and regulations
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	29
Title of training course	Live Agent CBRN Medical Responder – Individual Level Advanced
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	VVU Vyškov Field Live Chemical Agent Training Facility, Czech Republic
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Medical responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This course provides trained medical personnel with the knowledge, skills and abilities to analyse the medical risks at a CBRN or hazardous materials incident and to plan and implement procedures to respond to potential health impacts on response personnel in a pre-hospital setting.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical, physical and toxicological properties of CBRN agents • Identification of the signs and symptoms of exposure to CBRN materials, primarily chemical agents

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prediction of the potential behaviour of chemical agents • Planning the response by identifying the relevant equipment to support Hot Zone entries • Health hazards and risks associated with hot zone activities, standard and non-standard decontamination materials • Determination of hazard control zones • Determine the equipment and resources required for a medical monitoring station • Plan and implement a response to a medical emergency • Decontamination methodologies and processes • Establishing a medical monitoring station • Determine the requirement for pre-entry and post-entry medical monitoring of personnel involved in hot zone entries
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	30
Title of training course	CBRN Forensics – Individual Level Advanced
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	VVU Vyškov Field Live Chemical Agent Training Facility, Czech Republic
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Law enforcement, fire rescue, EMS, HAZMAT responders and other public safety officials
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	3 days (24 hours)
Course aim & content	This curriculum provides participants with the training and skills necessary to detect the clandestine manufacture of chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear and explosive weapons of mass destruction. (Note: This course can also be conducted as Live Agent Training, with a prerequisite of CBRN General Awareness Training).
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principles of Hot Zone forensics • Overview of CBRNE agent types, their symptoms and mechanism of entry • Identification of precursor ingredient • Identification of manufacturing equipment and processes • Overview of specialised personal protection equipment and respiratory protection equipment • Detection and monitoring techniques including searches, surveys, sampling, improvised explosive devices, and trap recognition and response • Overview of clandestine CBR laboratories • Sample collection procedures • Confined space procedures • Forced air ventilation techniques
Training method	Classroom training only (or as agreed)
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/individual-training/

No.	31
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Title of training course	Live Agent CBR Response Team Member – Collective Level Response Team Member
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Law enforcement, fire rescue, EMS, HAZMAT responders and other public safety officials
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	5 days (40 hours each C/B/R)
Course aim & content	This course is to provide response team members with advanced skills to analyse, plan and implement a response to a possible criminal or terrorist activity involving CBRN materials. This course meets the requirements for the intervention personnel to work in a team to survey or mitigate any CBRN incident. Participants train in safe working procedures under incident conditions, including advanced training on communication, decontamination, calculations, measurements, cartography, searching for CBRN materials in the field, basic sampling, and other relevant tasks.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Properties and effects of CBRN agents • Methods of dissemination of CBRN materials • Toxicology and first effects of CBRN materials • Terrorist action using CBRN materials • Team protection procedures (personal protective equipment, donning/doffing, avoidance of contamination) • Theory of decontamination and application of selected decontamination procedures and the setup of an Emergency Personal Decontamination Station (EPDS) • Management of contaminated personnel (casualties and responders) • Definition and marking of an initial hazardous CBRN area • CBRN hazard assessment techniques, pre and post blast, including X-ray • CBRN detection using available equipment an operator, pre and post blast • Potential outcomes of a CBRN incident
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/collective-training/#0a00014629a7fb310

No.	32
Title of training course	Nuclear Emergency Training – Collective Level Response Team Member
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	Chernobyl Exclusion Zone and Slavutych, Ukraine
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders, military personnel, scientists, nuclear industry, international organisations, NGO's, and governmental organisations
Max. attendance	6-12
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This course provides participants with an awareness of emergency measures after a nuclear accident.

Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiation safety • Consequences of a nuclear accident • Consequence management after a nuclear accident • Chernobyl 1986: causes and effects • Comparison of the Chernobyl/Fukushima incidents • Working in a radiologically contaminated area • Protection against open radioactive sources • Detection of radioactive sources in a contaminated environment • Sampling procedures • Decontamination procedures
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/collective-training/#0a00014629a7fb310

No.	33
Title of training course	Sampling and Identification of Biological, Chemical and Radiological Agents (SIBCRA) – Collective Level Response Team Member
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	6 weeks for all (B, C & R)
Course aim & content	The scope of this course is to provide first responders with the required competencies to investigate and collect samples of possible CBRN contamination in order to allow laboratories to conduct highly reliable scientific analysis of samples. This course is run in-line with the NATO SIBCRA standards. This course can be split into individual modules.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theory of SIRA (Sampling and Identification of Radiological Agents) • Properties of radiological agents and protection against their effects • Signs and symptoms of exposure to radiological agents • Principles of detection and decontamination • Principles of respiratory protection against radiological agents • Decision processes for the team leader and the roles within the team • The SIRA sampling kit • Search of radioactive sources, determining, and fencing off a contaminated area • Sampling techniques to avoid cross-contamination • Packaging techniques/transport of samples/chain of custody • Methods of analysis and interpretation of results • Practical scenario based exercises
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/collective-training/#0a00014629a7fb310

No.	34
Title of training course	Live Agent Sampling and Identification of Biological, Chemical and Radiological Agents (SIBCRA) – Collective Level Response Team Member
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	VVU Vyškov Field Live Chemical Agent Training Facility, Czech Republic
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	Min. 5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	To enable the operator to safely collect samples under hazardous conditions, including the ability to identify and accurately record the collection of samples and maintain chain of custody.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse observations and records of the reconnaissance team, photographs, witness statements and video recordings, etc. to identify the evidence available and the types of samples to be collected Develop a plan for the collection of samples Prepare and organise equipment for the collection of samples Conduct a sampling operation to safely collect a CBR sample Select personal protective equipment for use in a Hot Zone Decontaminate and seal a sample for transportation Plan how to maintain the chain of custody
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/collective-training/#0a00014629a7fb310

No.	35
Title of training course	Live Agent CBR Device Investigation – Collective Level Response Team Member
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	VVU Vyškov Field Live Chemical Agent Training Facility, Czech Republic
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	Min. 5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	The scope of this course is to provide EOD/IED qualified first responders who may be involved in a response to a possible criminal or terrorist activity involving CBRN devices with the skills to analyse, plan and implement an investigation of those IEDs in a potential hot zone.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse a CBR IED incident to determine the magnitude of the problem in terms of outcomes Properties of chemical agents Identification of the signs and symptoms of exposure to chemical agent Prediction models and methods for determining the dispersion of CBR Agents Plan a response by the identification and preparation of the relevant equipment for use within the Hot Zone Implement a planned response by using the relevant equipment to perform an investigation using pulsed X-rays inside the Hot Zone

Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/collective-training/#0a00014629a7fb310

No.	36
Title of training course	Live Agent CBR Response Team Leader – Collective Level Response Team Leader
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	VVU Vyškov Field Live Chemical Agent Training Facility, Czech Republic
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	Min. 5 days (40 hours) each C/B/R
Course aim & content	This course is to provide Response Team Leaders with advanced skills to analyse, plan and implement a response to a possible criminal or terrorist activity involving R materials.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The properties and effects of CWA, Toxic Industrial Materials (TIMs), biological and radiological agents • Methods of dissemination of CBR materials • Toxicology and first effects of CBR materials • Terrorist actions using CBR materials • Team protection procedures (personal protective equipment, donning/doffing, avoidance of contamination) • Theory of decontamination and application of selected decontamination procedures and the setup of an Emergency Personal Decontamination Station (EPDS) • Management of contaminated personnel (casualties and responders) • Definition and marking of an initial hazardous CBR area • CBR hazard assessment techniques, pre and post blast, including X-rays • CBR detection employing available equipment as user, pre and post blast • Potential outcomes of a CBRN incident
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/collective-training/#0a00014629a7fb310

No.	37
Title of training course	CBRN EOD Incident Commander – Command Level
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Command level responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	Min. 5 days (40 hours)

Course aim & content	This advanced level training is appropriate for command level responders with the responsibility of directing response efforts at a natural disaster or deliberate RN incident.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CBRNE agent overview • Personal protection equipment overview • Chemical agents of opportunity for terrorism • Incident Command Systems (ICS) • Pre-Incident plans and procedures • Incident management software programs • Stand-by/recall of emergency response personnel • Expedient chemical/biological release mitigation methods • Procedures for prolonged SCBA/PPE operations • Manpower rehabilitation and replacement logistics for sustained operations • Stress management for emergency personnel • Mass decontamination • Overview of human behaviour during a CBRN crisis • Use of aviation assets/airspace management • Stockpile and distribution plans • Security of critical facilities • Medical emergency operations plans • Multiple agency communication • Criminal investigation of deliberate CBRNE events • Long-term response and recovery • Environmental concerns • Emerging/next generation response technologies case studies
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/hzs-training-command-courses/

No.	38
Title of training course	CBRNE Airport/Border Crossing Security – Command Level
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Command level responders at border crossings, airports, shipping ports
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	A command level course for supervisors at border crossings, airports, shipping ports for CBRN related devices, containers and luggage.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Properties and effects of CWA, TIMs, biological and radiological agents • Categories of CBRNE devices (CBRN IED's, CBRN DD's and CBRN SD's) • Handling of dangerous materials • The different classes of CBRNE materials and identify differences in their properties • Recognition of the first effects of exposure to CBRNE materials through physical signs and symptoms • The typical behaviour of people who may be carrying CBRNE material or potential CBRNE devices

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The basis of detection and screening of CBRNE materials and the identification using both fixed and portable detection and screening systems • Self-protection and the protection of those in the immediate vicinity of a CBRNE device • The basis of personal protective equipment, decontamination, and individual protection procedures (IPE, donning/doffing, avoidance on contamination) • Theory of decontamination and application of selected decontamination procedures (e.g. immediate decontamination of personnel) • Definition and marking of an initial hazardous CBR area • CBR hazard area, pre and post blast • CBR detection employing available equipment as user, pre and post blast • National and international rules and regulations
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/hzs-training-command-courses/

No.	39
Title of training course	CBRNE Special Event Planning and Management – Command Level
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Command level responders
Max. attendance	Classroom capacity
Course duration	Min. 5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This advanced level training is appropriate for command level responders. The scope of this course covers RN threats for special events. Event types include festivals, concerts, carnivals, block parties, sporting events, marathons and protests.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CBRNE threat analysis • Planning and research for events • Developing maintenance of traffic plans • Special event liability • Conducting an event threat and vulnerability analysis • Public safety • Neighbourhood/community support • Event staffing levels • Protestor issues • Incident command system • Entry screening
Training method	Classroom training only
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/hzs-training-command-courses/

No.	40
Title of training course	CBRNE Threat and Vulnerability Assessments – Command Level
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Command level responders
Max. attendance	Classroom capacity
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	This course provides participants with the knowledge, skills and abilities to conduct a threat analysis and to assess the vulnerability of their organisation, enabling security and emergency managers to better understand the current readiness posture of their organisation.
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible attack threat scenarios (identify, categorise, and prioritise) • Essential functions critical to business continuity and eventual recovery • Organisation’s internal and external environments • Operational factors that could possibility lead to a terrorist attack Vulnerability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas of vulnerability • Evaluation of vulnerabilities against potential attack threat scenarios • Effectiveness of countermeasures • Additional control measures
Training method	Classroom training only
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/hzs-training-command-courses/

No.	41
Title of training course	Planning a Response to a CBRNE EOD Incident – Command Level
Organizer	Hotzone Solutions
Country	The Netherlands
Co-organizer(s)/Location	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Command level responders
Max. attendance	20
Course duration	5 days (40 hours)
Course aim & content	<p>This course provides participants with the knowledge, skills and abilities to analyse the risks at a hazardous materials or weapons of mass destruction incident; and to plan and implement safety procedures of responders during hot and warm zone operations. The course is based on the competencies for HAZMAT Safety Officers as outlined in NFPA 472, Standard for Competence of Responders to a Hazardous Materials/Weapons of Mass Destruction Incidents and provides Safety Officers with the core competencies of Safety Officers as defined in Chapter 11 of NFPA 472.</p> <p>Content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse a CBRNE incident • Determine the complexity of the scene for safety • Evaluate hazard and response information
Learning objectives	<p>Plan a safe response within the capabilities of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available response personnel

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal protective equipment, and • Control equipment • Implement a safe response • Assess an incident action plan, emergency response plan, and/or standard operating procedures • Evaluate the progress of the planned response • Terminating an incident response
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	https://hotzonesolutions.org/solutions/hzs-training/hzs-training-command-courses/

2.5 Qatar CBRN Academy, Qatar

Qatar CBRN Academy training courses address all categories of first responders, as well as member of the general public who might be involved in a real incident with radiological agents due to an accident or a terrorist attack in an urban environment. This includes the need to be adequately prepared to save responders' lives in order to be able to save others in need.⁷

Qatar CBRN Academy training programme encompasses at least 7 international RN courses listed below:

- Basic CBRN Course;
- Radiation Safety Awareness Course;
- CBRN Detection Course;
- CBRN Medical Course;
- CBRN Decontamination Course;
- CBRN Decontamination of Service Animals;
- CBRN Decontamination of Special Groups and Disabled People.

No.	42
Title of training course	Basic CBRN Course
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	CBRN First Responders (Police; Fire Service; Ambulance Crews; ED and Nuclear Medicine Personnel), Public Health personnel, Civil Protection personnel
Max. attendance	
Course duration	5 days
Course content	This classroom course familiarises participants with different types of CBRN threats and their consequences on the human body.

⁷ The current situation regarding the provision of these training courses is unclear (status: 15 December 2020) The information about the courses was last accessed on 30 April 2020 at <http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training>.

Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CBRN threats and their consequences on human body • Adjust existing emergency response plans to new emerging threats • Organize adequate response system (police, fire service, ambulance service and hospital health service) • Dehydration and stress wearable sensors for field first responders
Training method	Classroom training
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training

No.	43
Title of training course	Radiation Safety Awareness Course
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	CBRN First Responders (Police; Fire Service; Ambulance Crews; ED and Nuclear Medicine Personnel), Public Health personnel, Civil Protection personnel, Coronary Service personnel, Oil/gas personnel, Cargo companies (air; sea; land)
Max. attendance	
Course duration	4 days
Course content	This classroom course familiarises participants with the different types of radiation, detection principles, and protective measures and strategies. A scenario-based tabletop exercise is conducted at the end of the course. This course should be completed before any other course.
Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Types of radiation • Detection technologies • Protective measures • Protective equipment • Decontamination principles
Training method	Classroom training with a scenario-based tabletop exercise
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training

No.	44
Title of training course	CBRN Detection Course
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	CBRN First Responders (Police; Fire Service; Ambulance Crews; ED and Nuclear Medicine Personnel), Public Health personnel, Civil Protection personnel, Coronary Service personnel, Oil/gas personnel, Cargo companies (air; sea; land)
Max. attendance	
Course duration	2 days

Course content	This course covers detection technologies and systems associated with chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear and explosive agents. Detailed knowledge of pros and cons of each available technology in the decision process on the combinations required to achieve reliable results under various operational conditions and settings.
Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with (inter alia): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current detection capabilities and limitations • Radiological agent detection instruments • Emerging detection technologies • Detection exercises with simulants (where applicable)
Training method	Classroom training with hands-on exercises
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training

No.	45
Title of training course	CBRN Medical Course
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Physicians (hospital; private; military), Nurses (hospital; private; military), Medical technicians
Max. attendance	
Course duration	3 days
Course content	This course is aiming to disseminate specialized knowledge to medical sector and public health personnel that will be involved in a real CBRN incident in urban environment.
Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with (inter alia): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiological Dispersal/Emitting Devices (RDD/REDs) • Radiological accidents • Nuclear weapons (uses; accidents) • Effects of CBRN agent on human body • CBRN field triage and decontamination • First Aids in a contaminated environment • Personal & collective protection equipment & usage • Update on CBRN detection technologies • Health sector CBRN preparedness and response
Training method	Classroom training
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training

No.	46
Title of training course	CBRN Decontamination Course
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International

Target audience	CBRN First Responders (police; fire service; ambulance crews), Civil Defense officials, Public Health officials, Military CBRN officers
Max. attendance	
Course duration	3 or 5 days
Course content	This course covers mass decontamination protocols, systems, and technologies associated with chemical, biological and radiological agents. If practical training is required, trainees should deploy their own PPEs and decontamination equipment in order to enhance their dexterities and check their field protocols. If this is the case, the duration of the course will be extended to 5 days. Proof of good health status will be also required.
Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with (inter alia): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why female first responders in decontamination stations? • Current decontamination capabilities • Chemical agent decontamination technologies and limitations • Biological agent decontamination technologies and processes • Explosive detection instruments and processes • Decontamination of wounded contaminated victims • Emerging technologies
Training method	Classroom training, practical training
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training

No.	47
Title of training course	CBRN Decontamination of Service Animals
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	Police K9 personnel (narcotics; EOD; guard), Military service dogs personnel (EOD; guard), Blind people (can attend the course with their dogs), Zoo personnel
Max. attendance	
Course duration	n. a.
Course content	Both police and the military but also certain disabled people use service dogs that might be exposed to CBRN agents together with their handlers or owners. Special decontamination protocols should be used and practiced during peace time, since in a chaotic real incident environment it would be difficult to have dogs properly behave and stand in line to be decontaminated. This course is composed in collaboration with Qatari veterinarians and the University of Qatar. NOTE : Due the very specialized content of this course it will be conducted only ONCE a year and only if adequate numbers of attendees is achieved. It can also be tailor-made for a specific organization of governmental body.
Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with (inter alia): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiological tolerance of service animals • Decontamination of service animals
Training method	Classroom training
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/http://www.qcbrna.qa/Training

No.	48
Title of training course	CBRN Decontamination of Special Groups and Disabled People
Organizer	Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A)
Country	Qatar
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	CBRN First Responders (police; fire service; ambulance crews), Civil Defense officials, Public Health officials, Military CBRN officers
Max. attendance	
Course duration	3 days
Course content	During the mass decontamination process victims might belong to special or disabled groups that require special approach and techniques. The special group is composed of children (all ages), pregnant women, homeless, tourists, and the elderly. Usually during decontamination drills it is assumed that victims are all ambulatory. This course also addresses the needs of people who are deaf or blind, on wheelchairs or with paraplegia or with chronic diseases in the midst of a chaotic environment.
Learning objectives	Familiarize participants with (inter alia): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current decontamination capabilities • Radiological agent decontamination technologies, process, residual contamination control • Decontamination of wounded contaminated victims • Emerging technologies • Decontamination and the Sharia Law • Visit to a special hospital department where disabled people are treated • Visit to a maternity hospital to discuss with pregnant women about chemical antidotes, radiation peels, and decontamination issues along with their fears and reserves
Training method	Classroom training, practical training
Weblink	https://web.archive.org/web/20190426223727/

2.6 CBRN Academy, Sweden

CBRN Academy assists companies, governments and states in maintaining a high level of knowledge and preparedness regarding CBRN hazards and accidents that may occur. It also supports businesses and governments in their efforts to comply with current legislation.

CBRN Academy provides analysis, documentation, education and protection in the field of CBRN. The focus is (a) on the provision of expertise and products to businesses, governments and states to minimize risk, and (b) to increase the capacity to successfully handle a CBRN related incident.⁸

CBRN Academy offers the *Advanced Radiation and Nuclear (RN) Training Course* described below.

⁸ <http://cbrnacademy.se/>

No.	49
Title of training course	Advanced (R&N) Radiation and Nuclear Training Course
Organizer	CBRN Academy
Country	Sweden
Co-organizer(s)	
Course type (national, international)	International
Target audience	First Responders, NGO's, Civil Defence, Police/Security Personnel, Medical, Municipal (city) services and civil- / corporate organizations
Max. attendance	20-25
Course duration	2 weeks (80 hours)
Course content	Basic types of radiation (alpha, beta, gamma, neutron); Isotopes; Scale, Safety and Risk; Sources of Radiation; Medical Effects of Radiation
Learning objectives	<p>Week 1. Familiarize participants with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source of radiation (Medical, Industrial, Scientific) • Overview of Nuclear Power Plants and Accidents • Radiological Terrorism • Historical studies of Radiation incidents • Nuclear Smuggling • Introduction to Radiation Detection • Radiation Detection: Dosimeters and Dosimetry (Equipment TBD) • Radiation Detection: Detection and Monitoring (Equipment TBD) • Radiation Detection: Isotope Identification (Equipment TBD) • Radiological Dispersal Devices "Dirty Bombs" • Radiological Decontamination • Response to a suspected RDD "Dirty Bomb" incident <p>Week 2. Familiarize participants with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nuclear Weapons and Fallout • Medical Effects of Radiation • Forensics and Evidence in Radiation Terrorism Incidents • Common sources of false alarms • Forensics and Evidence in Radiation Terrorism Incidents • Common sources of false alarms • Radiation Detection in the Port and Border Environment – Cars and Trucks • Radiation Detection in the Port and Border Environment – Cargo and Containers • Medical Isotopes and why they make radiation detection difficult • Radiation Detection in the Fixed Facility Protection Environment • Radiation detection in the Urban environment
Training method	Classroom and practical training
Weblink	http://cbrnacademy.se/

3 ANALYSIS

The survey identified altogether 49 RN-related training courses offered to the international community of first responders and emergency managers.⁹

These RN training courses were analysed with regard to:

- 1) Course Organizers
- 2) Learning Objectives
- 3) Target Audience
- 4) Scope and Content
- 5) Training Method
- 6) Level of Training
- 7) Duration of the Training Course.

3.1 Course Organizers

The survey identified the following organisations conducting international RN-related training courses:

- Seibersdorf CBRN Academy, Austria;
- Joint CBRN Defence Center of Excellence (JCBRNDCOE), Czech Republic;
- International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Austria;
- Hotzone Solutions Group, The Netherlands;
- Qatar CBRN Academy (Q-CBRN-A), Qatar;
- CBRN Academy, Sweden.

3.2 Learning Objectives

The above training courses cover a wide spectrum of *learning objectives*. The following section groups the main topic areas and lists the associated subjects for each topic area.

3.2.1 Fundamentals of ionizing radiation and radioactive material

Goal: Concepts of ionizing radiation, its sources, properties, units of measure and characteristics of ionizing radiation.

- Understand the basics in radiation protection;
- Sources of Radiation (Natural);
- Source of radiation (Medical, Industrial, Scientific);

⁹ Status: 9 December 2020

- Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources;
- Knowledge on chemical and physical properties of RN;
- Prediction of the potential behaviour of RN agents;
- Historical studies of radiation incidents;
- Principles of radiological decontamination.

3.2.2 Biological and medical effects of radiation

Goal: Principles of management of RN casualties

- Working as a first responder in a Hot Zone (selection and use of protective equipment);
- Planning the response by identifying the relevant equipment to support Hot Zone entries;
- Health hazards and risks associated with Hot Zone activities;
- First Aid in a contaminated environment;
- Personal & collective protection equipment and its usage;
- Identification of signs and symptoms of exposure to RN;
- Responding first at the scene, managing overexposed or contaminated patients;
- Setting up the emergency area;
- Transferring patients;
- Protecting responders;
- Dealing with RN casualties inside and outside the Hot Zone;
- Diagnosis and radiological considerations and advanced techniques and methods to diagnose, assess and treat overexposed individuals;
- Chemical and physical properties of RN agents;
- Determine the equipment and resources required for a medical monitoring station;
- Decontamination methodologies and processes;
- Establishing a medical monitoring station;
- Determine the requirement for pre-entry and post-entry medical monitoring of personnel involved in Hot Zone entries;
- Female first responders in decontamination stations;
- Decontamination of wounded contaminated victims;
- Emerging technologies.

3.2.3 Radiation Detection

Goal: Identification of radioactive material and radioactive commodities

- Familiarization with detection of RN materials;
- Dosimeters and Dosimetry;

- Detection and Monitoring;
- Isotope Identification⁴
- Familiarity with orphan and misused sources⁴
- Practical detection exercises with simulants (where applicable);
- Emerging detection technologies.

3.2.4 Radiation Protection

Goal: Installation of radiation safety program management;

- Understand how to protect themselves and the public from contamination;
- Gain confidence in the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) in a live environment;
- Understand and be able to apply safe work practices;
- Team protection procedures.

3.2.5 Survey

Goal: Planning and preparing for reconnaissance operations

- Theory of SIRA (Sampling and Identification of Radiological Agents);
- The SIRA sampling kit;
- Develop a plan for the collection of samples;
- Analyse observations and records of the reconnaissance team, photographs, witness statements and video recordings, etc. to identify the evidence available and the types of samples to be collected;
- Prepare and organise equipment for the collection of samples;
- Select PPE for use in a Hot Zone;
- Decontaminate and seal a sample for transportation;
- Plan how to maintain the chain of custody.

3.2.6 Decontamination

Goal: Principles of personal protection, agent detection, recognition and emergency treatment of agent exposure

- Understand the principles of radioactive contamination and decontamination;
- Understand and be able to apply safe work practices;
- Radiological agent decontamination technologies, process, residual contamination control;

- Theory of decontamination and application of selected decontamination procedures and the setup of an Emergency Personal Decontamination Station (EPDS);
- Gain confidence in how to safely and efficiently decontaminate equipment, vehicles and personnel;
- Gain confidence in the use of PPE in a live environment;
- Emergency decontamination (materials and procedures);
- Standard and non-standard decontamination materials;
- Definition and marking of an initial hazardous R area;
- R hazard area, pre- and post-blast of an RDD;
- Management of a contaminated operator;
- Understand how to handle radioactive waste;
- Radiological tolerance of service animals;
- Decontamination of service animals;
- Decontamination of wounded contaminated victims;
- Decontamination and the Law;
- Visit to a special hospital department where disabled people are treated;
- Visit to a maternity hospital to discuss with pregnant women about chemical antidotes, radiation peels, and decontamination issues along with their fears and reserve;
- Emerging technologies.

3.2.7 Radiological and Nuclear Terrorism

Goal: Identification of the difference between RN incidents and other hazardous material incidents, and countermeasures.

- Nuclear Smuggling;
- Radiological Terrorism;
- Radiological Dispersal Devices (RDD; "Dirty Bombs");
- Forensics and evidence in radiation terrorism incidents;
- Response to a suspected RDD "Dirty Bomb" incident;
- R detection employing available equipment as user, pre- and post-blast;
- Protection of forensic evidence pre- and post-blast;
- Definition and marking of an initial hazardous RN area;
- RN hazard assessment techniques, pre- and post- blast, including X-ray;
- RN detection using available equipment an operator, pre-and post-blast;
- Potential outcomes of an RN incident;
- Principles of Hot Zone forensics;
- Collection of pre- and post-blast information and evidence;

- Provision of specialist RN EOD (Explosive Ordnance Disposal) technical advice for a higher command;
- Coordination with RN specialists in a RN/EOD incident;
- Overview of NR agent types, their symptoms and mechanism of entry;
- Identification of precursor ingredient;
- Identification of manufacturing equipment and processes;
- Overview of PPE equipment and respiratory protection equipment;
- Detection and monitoring techniques including searches, surveys, sampling, IED, and trap recognition and response;
- Overview of clandestine R laboratories;
- Sample collection procedures;
- Confined space procedures;
- Forced air ventilation techniques;
- Properties and effects of RN agents;
- Methods of dissemination of RN materials;
- First effects of RN materials;
- Terrorist action using RN materials;
- Overview of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE);
- Team protection procedures (PPE, donning/doffing, avoidance of contamination);
- Procedures for prolonged PPE operations;
- Management of contaminated personnel (casualties and responders);
- Analyse an RDD incident to determine the magnitude of the problem in terms of outcomes;
- Prediction models and methods for determining the dispersion of R agents;
- Plan a response by the identification and preparation of the relevant equipment for use within the Hot Zone;
- Implement a planned response by using the relevant equipment to perform an investigation using pulsed X-rays inside the Hot Zone;
- Incident Command Systems (ICS);
- Pre-Incident plans and procedures;
- Incident management software programs;
- Stand-by/recall of emergency response personnel;
- Manpower rehabilitation and replacement logistics for sustained operations;
- Stress management for emergency personnel;
- Mass decontamination;
- Overview of human behaviour during an RN crisis;
- Use of aviation assets/airspace management;

- Stockpile and distribution plans;
- Security of critical facilities;
- Medical emergency operations plan;
- Multiple agency communication;
- Criminal investigation of deliberate RN events;
- Long-term response and recovery;
- Environmental concerns;
- Different classes of RN materials and differences in their properties;
- Categories of RN devices (IED, RDD);
- Recognition of the first effects of exposure to RN materials through physical signs and symptoms;
- Typical behaviour of people who may be carrying RN material or potential RN devices;
- The basis of detection and screening of RN materials and the identification using both fixed and portable detection and screening systems;
- Self-protection and the protection of those in the immediate vicinity of an RN device;
- Theory of decontamination and application of selected decontamination procedures (e.g., immediate decontamination of personnel);
- Definition and marking of an initial hazardous R area;
- R hazard area, pre- and post-blast;
- RN threats and their consequences on human body;
- Adjustment of existing emergency response plans to new emerging threats;
- Organization of adequate response system (police, fire service, ambulance service and hospital health service);
- Dehydration and stress wearable sensors for field first responders;
- Emerging/next generation response technologies case studies;
- National and international rules and regulations.

3.2.8 Nuclear Emergencies

Goal: Familiarization of participants with the various elements of nuclear emergencies.

- Overview of nuclear power plant (NPP) operation, incidents and accidents;
- Nuclear weapons and fallout;
- Medical effects of radiation;
- Forensics and evidence in radiation terrorism incidents;
- Common sources of false alarms;
- Radiation detection in the port and border environment – cars and trucks;
- Radiation detection in the port and border environment – cargo and containers;

- Medical isotopes and why they make radiation detection difficult;
- Radiation detection in a fixed facility protection environment;
- Familiarity with Special Nuclear Material (SNM);
- Overview on how to prepare for nuclear emergencies;
- Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources;
- Familiarity with the use of detection equipment in nuclear emergency situations;
- Gain confidence in the use of PPE in a live environment;
- Understand and be able to apply safe work practices with radioisotopes;
- Developing procedures for on-site and off-site protective actions;
- Establishing response teams, including structuring their roles and responsibilities;
- Organising emergency response actions at a nuclear power reactor site;
- Reviewing the threat category of a research reactor site;
- Radiation safety;
- Consequence management after a nuclear accident;
- Chernobyl 1986: causes and effects;
- Comparison of the Chernobyl/Fukushima accidents;
- Working in a radiologically contaminated area;
- Protection against open radioactive sources;
- Detection of radioactive sources in a contaminated environment;
- Sampling procedures;
- Decontamination procedures.

3.2.9 Incident Commander

Goal: Understand the basics of the incident commanders' tasks and responsibilities.

- Be familiar with different radiological incidents;
- Understand the Incident Command Systems (ICS);
- Learn how to support/ be the incident commander;
- Learn the basics of the warning and reporting system;
- Understand the principles of command and control in relation to RN incidents;
- Understand the implications of bilateral or international assistance for local first responders;
- Identify principal NATO and EU Crisis Management (CM) bodies, systems and procedures, and explain the NATO and EU CM process;
- Explain CM after RN incident;
- Gain confidence in the work with sealed and open radioactive sources;

- Be familiar with the use of detection equipment;
- Gain confidence in the use of PPE in a live environment;
- Understand and be able to apply safe work practices;
- Be able to draft pre-Incident plans and procedures;
- Understand Incident Management Software Programs;
- Be familiar with the principles of Stand-by/Recall of Emergency Response Personnel;
- Be familiar with the procedures for prolonged operations involving Self-Contained Breathing Apparatus (SCBA) and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE);
- Understand manpower rehabilitation and replacement logistics for sustained operations;
- Understand stress management for emergency personnel;
- Be familiar with mass decontamination;
- Have an overview on human behaviour during an RN crisis;
- Understand the use of aviation assets;
- Be familiar with the security of Critical Facilities;
- Be familiar with Medical Emergency Operations Plans;
- Understand Multiple Agency Communication;
- Understand the criminal investigation of deliberate RN events;
- Be able to plan long term response and recovery;
- Recognize environmental concerns;
- Be familiar with case studies;
- Understand the principles of command and control in relation to RN incidents;
- Understand the implications of bilateral or international assistance for local first responders;
- Explain *Lessons Learned* from recent NATO and EU commitments and exercises;
- Identify the importance of Rules of Engagement, Process and Public Information during the planning and implementation of Crisis Response Operations;
- Have an overview on Emerging/Next Generation Response Technologies.

3.2.10 Emergency Preparedness Coordinators

Goal: Assist organisations in managing exercises by testing preparedness for nuclear or radiological emergencies.

- Understand the security context behind national and international RN preparedness and response;
- Understand the methods employed to recognise a RN incident;
- Understand the protection of responders and safety of victims;
- Understand the decontamination options at an RN incident;

- Understand basic medical and psychological considerations in relation to RN incidents;
- Understand the basic principles of detection and sample taking;
- Understand the principles of command and control in relation to RN incidents;
- Understand the implications of bilateral or international assistance for local first responders.
- Explain assessment of radiological hazard and establishment of an inner cordoned area;
- Explain exposure pathways and protective actions;
- Explain field triage for mass casualty events;
- Explain monitoring and decontamination of the public, responders, vehicles and equipment
- Dosimetric criteria (generic criteria and reference levels);
- Emergency planning zones and distances;
- Hazard assessment and categories;
- Protection of emergency workers;
- Protection strategies;
- Training on the concepts and operational response steps recommended for first responders;
- Increase national capability to protect members of the public in case of an accidental release at an NPP;
- Improve public understanding of radiation-risk related issues;
- Strengthening Member States' capacity to communicate effectively with the public in a nuclear or radiological emergency;
- Teach basic issues related to risk perception, media relations and spokesperson selection;
- Evaluate the progress of the planned response;
- Terminating an incident response.

3.2.11 Response Processes and Capabilities

Goal: Planning and response considerations for reconnaissance operations in an RN event.

- Relevant equipment to support Hot Zone entries;
- Health hazards and risks associated with Hot Zone activities;
- Equipment and resources needed for a medical monitoring station;
- Necessary communication with other personnel on-scene;
- Practical principles of detection and protection;
- Establishing safety zones and safe distances;
- Use of protective equipment (personal and collective);
- Personal dosimetry;
- Record keeping of exposure;

- Provision of advice to local authorities;
- Adherence to national and international rules and regulations;
- Necessary steps to declare the formal end to a nuclear or radiological emergency.

3.3 Target Audience

The training courses identified address the following target audiences:

- Law enforcement, fire rescue, EMS, HAZMAT responders, other public safety officials, and military personnel;
- Scientists, nuclear industry, international organisations, NGO's, and governmental organisations;
- Emergency response personnel (radiation protection specialists, first responders, law enforcement, and emergency managers) with minimal training in radiological emergency response or experienced professionals seeking refresher training;
- RN trainers with substantial experience in fire and rescue, police or paramedic services, or similar activities (civilian and military) and with training activities in this field;
- Key elements of consequence management structures, including the police, firefighters, health services, hospitals, military, civil defence, emergency management authorities, public information, specialist teams (such as counterterrorism units or investigation);
- Emergency preparedness coordinators who have a key role in the organization of exercises, such as: technical and scientific support who lead the development of exercise scenarios and simulated radiological data; emergency planners, and training specialists;
- Medical first responders, emergency medical technicians, ambulance attendants and other medical personnel who may be called to respond to a radiological emergency or emergencies at nuclear facilities;
- Emergency physicians, nursing staff, support staff and medical administrators who may be called upon to manage critical care for overexposed, contaminated or potentially contaminated patients;
- Medical specialists who manage the care for severely exposed or internally contaminated patients;
- Decision-makers, local and facility emergency planners, emergency response coordinators and emergency managers in a nuclear or radiological emergency, including public information officers and emergency preparedness and response experts at local and national levels;
- Professionals responsible for communicating with the public and the media, as well as those in charge of coordinating official information in a nuclear or radiological emergency, including public information officers and emergency preparedness and response experts at local and national levels;
- Professionals working in preparedness for and response to nuclear or radiological emergencies at the national, regional, local or facility levels;
- Command level responders at border crossings, airports, shipping ports;
- Ambulance Crews, ED and Nuclear Medicine Personnel, Public Health personnel, Civil Protection personnel, Coronary Service personnel, Oil/gas personnel, Cargo companies (air;

- sea; land);
- Municipal (city) services and civil- / corporate organizations.

3.4 Scope and Content

Reflecting the different target audiences, scope and content of the international training course identified vary as much. Below scope and content of these courses are categorized into *Basic Level Training* and *Advanced Level Training*.

3.4.1 Basic Level Training

- Basic radiation knowledge and understanding, including the handling of detection devices
- Principles of radiation detection
- Radiological search operations and mission planning
- Personal protective equipment
- Radioactive material identification and characterization
- Radiation contamination and source recovery
- Generic criteria for use in preparedness for and response to a radiation emergency
- Response and assistance network
- Incident and emergency communication
- Principles of decontamination in case of radiological incidents, under the safe use of unsealed radioactive emitters
- Introduction to the *International CBRN Training Curriculum for Trainers of First Responders*; enhancement of interoperability among first responders in an international response to CBRN events
- First response organisation functions, i.e., assessment of radiological hazard and establishment of an inner cordoned area; exposure pathways and protective actions; field triage for mass casualty events; monitoring and decontamination of the public, responders, vehicles and equipment
- Communication principles and tools that assist public information officers in preparing for communication, helping to mitigate the emergency's effects
- Basic know-how to (a) detect radiological agents, (b) protect humans and critical infrastructure from radiation emitting sources, and (c) implement appropriate health and safety measures
- Emergency measures after a nuclear accident
- Concepts, terminology and introduces a process for the preparation, conduct and evaluation of an exercise, including general concepts of exercises; the preparation process and exercise manual; exercise objectives; scenario, injects and data; radiological data for exercises, and exercise evaluation

- Response at the scene, including medical first responders, emergency medical technicians, ambulance attendants and other medical personnel who may be called to respond to a radiological emergency or emergencies at nuclear facilities
- Response at the hospital, including emergency physicians, nursing staff, support staff and medical administrators who may be called upon to manage critical care for overexposed, contaminated or potentially contaminated patients
- Preparation of a public communication programme with a strategy that is tailored to relevant scenarios and key audiences
- Basic types of radiation (alpha, beta, gamma, neutron); Isotopes; Scale, Safety and Risk; Sources of Radiation; Medical Effects of Radiation
- Different types of radiation, detection principles, and protective measures
- Detection technologies and systems associated with radiological and nuclear agents
- Decontamination systems and technologies associated with radiological agents
- Directing response efforts at a deliberate RN incident
- Different types of CBRN threats and their consequences on the human body
- RN threats for special events, including festivals, concerts, carnivals, block parties, sporting events, marathons and protests
- Security and emergency managers to carry out threat analysis and assessment of the vulnerability of their organisation, enabling them to better understand the current readiness posture of their organisation
- Mass decontamination protocols, systems, and technologies associated with radiological agents
- Police, military and also certain disabled people use service dogs that might be exposed to CBRN agents together with their handlers or owners, needing special decontamination techniques and procedures
- Decontamination process for special or disabled groups that require special approach and techniques, such as: children (all ages), pregnant women, homeless, tourists, and the elderly

3.4.2 Advanced Level Training

- Physical training with different radioisotopes, learning the effects of RN materials and the measures they can take to protect themselves against them
- Knowledge, skills and abilities to analyze the medical risks at a hazardous materials- or weapons of mass destruction incident; to plan and implement procedures to respond to potential health impacts on response personnel in a pre-hospital setting
- Various elements of nuclear emergencies, having its cause in accidents at NPPs or incidents involving SNM
- Response to radiation emergencies, originating from either radiation accidents, orphan sources, illicit trafficking or the malicious use of radioactive material
- Management of radiological emergencies, originating from either nuclear incidents (NPP/IND), orphan sources or misuse/illicit trafficking. The participants will also learn consequence

management and the basics in warning and reporting

- Search and respond to a portal alarm, consequence management in the event of a release of radiological material, and events ranging from a small, localized release to a larger incident, such as deployment of a radiological dispersal device
- Early diagnosis, general management, treatment and other elements related to the organisation of the medical response
- Action guides for the facility emergency response team, instructions, practical procedures, and tools that can be adapted to build a basic capability in response to a research reactor emergency
- Public protective actions in the event of an emergency involving actual or projected severe fuel damage in a light water reactor or spent fuel pool
- Early diagnosis, general management, treatment and other elements related to the organisation of the medical response
- Action guides for the facility emergency response team, instructions, practical procedures, and tools that can be adapted to build a basic capability in response to a research reactor emergency
- Advanced medical care, including medical specialists who manage the care for severely exposed or internally contaminated patients
- Procedures for adapting and lifting protective actions; medical follow-up and provision of mental health and psychosocial support; infrastructural elements necessary to support adequate capability for response during the transition phase, and the facilitation of smooth and prompt resumption of social and economic activity
- Detection of clandestine manufacture of radiological and nuclear weapons of mass destruction
- Advanced skills to analyse, plan and implement a response to a possible criminal or terrorist activity involving RN materials
- Specialized knowledge to medical sector and public health personnel that will be involved in a real CBRN incident in urban environment
- Supervisors at border crossings, airports, shipping ports for RN related devices, containers and luggage
- Analysis of the risks at a hazardous materials or weapons of mass destruction incident; planning and implementation of safety procedures of responders during hot and warm zone operations.

3.5 Training Methods and Course Duration

The table below lists the training methods and course duration used in the RN-related training courses (Table 1; training course number refers to numbering in this document, section ANALYSIS).

Relatively few groups offer -besides classroom training – also practical, hands-on training. Some groups focus on Internet-based distance learning.

The in-depth of the training content is reflected the course duration, i.e., some courses last only a few hours, whilst others last up to 7 or more days.

No.	Title of Training Course	Training Methods	Duration
1	RAD Basic Course	Classroom and practical training	60 hours
2	Basic CBRN Course – Individual Level	Classroom and practical training	100 hours
3	CBRN Medical Responder Course – Individual Level	Classroom and practical training	40 hours
4	Nuclear Emergency Preparedness Course – Individual Level	Classroom and practical training	60 hours
5	Radiation Emergency Response Course – Group Level	Classroom and practical training	60 hours
6	CBRN Incident Response Course – Group Level	Classroom and practical training	40 hours
7	Nuclear Emergency Response Course – Group Level	Classroom and practical training	60 hours
8	Radiation Decontamination Course – Group Level	Classroom and practical training	40 hours
9	Radiation Incident Commander Course – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	60 hours
10	CBRNE (CBRN EOD) Incident Commander Course – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	80 hours
11	International Radiological Assistance Program Training for Emergency Response (I-RAPTER) Basic Course	Briefings, equipment demonstrations and field exercises	5 days
12	International Radiological and Nuclear Training for Emergency Response (I-RAD) Basic Course	Briefings, equipment demonstrations and field exercises	5 days
13	Introduction to the International CBRN Training Curriculum for Trainers of First Responders to CBRN Incidents Course 2020	Briefings, equipment demonstrations	5 days
14	Consequence Management After a CBRN Incident Course	Briefings	5 days
15	Evaluating Preparedness for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency	Classroom workshops	5 days
16	First Response to a Radiological Emergency	Classroom workshops	4 days
17	Preparedness and Response for a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency	Classroom and practical training	5 days
18	Medical Response to a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency	Classroom workshops	9 days
19	Preparedness and Response for an Emergency at a Research Reactor	Classroom workshops	5 days
20	Protecting the Public During a Nuclear Power Reactor Emergency	Classroom workshops	5 days
21	Communication with the Public in a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency	Classroom workshops	5 days

22	Workshop on Arrangements for the Termination of a Nuclear or Radiological Emergency	Classroom workshops	4 days
23	CBRN General Awareness Training – Individual Level Awareness	Classroom workshops	5 days
24	Radiation Safety Awareness – Individual Level Awareness	Classroom workshops	4 days
25	CBRN Detection – Individual Level Awareness	Classroom workshops and practical training	5 days
26	CBRN Decontamination – Individual Level Awareness	Classroom workshops	5 days
27	CBRN Medical – Individual Level Awareness	Classroom workshops	3 days
28	Live Agent Training Radiological – Individual Level Advanced	Classroom and practical training	5 days
29	Live Agent CBRN Medical Responder – Individual Level Advanced	Classroom and practical training	5 days
30	CBRN Forensics – Individual Level Advanced	Classroom training (or as agreed)	3 days
31	Live Agent CBR Response Team Member – Collective Level Response Team Member	Classroom and practical training	5 days
32	Nuclear Emergency Training – Collective Level Response Team Member	Classroom and practical training	5 days
33	Sampling and Identification of Biological, Chemical and Radiological Agents (SIBCRA) – Collective Level Response Team Member	Classroom and practical training	6 weeks
34	Live Agent Sampling and Identification of Biological, Chemical and Radiological Agents (SIBCRA) – Collective Level Response Team Member	Classroom and practical training	5 days
35	Live Agent CBR Device Investigation – Collective Level Response Team Member	Classroom and practical training	5 days
36	Live Agent CBR Response Team Leader – Collective Level Response Team Leader	Classroom and practical training	5 days
37	CBRN EOD Incident Commander – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	5 days
38	CBRNE Airport/Border Crossing Security – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	5 days
39	CBRNE Special Event Planning and Management – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	5 days
40	CBRNE Threat and Vulnerability Assessments – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	5 days
41	Planning a Response to a CBRNE EOD Incident – Command Level	Classroom and practical training	5 days
42	Basic CBRN Course	Classroom training	5 days
43	Radiation Safety Awareness Course	Classroom training with a scenario-based tabletop exercise	4 days

44	CBRN Detection Course	Classroom training with hands-on exercises	2 days
45	CBRN Medical Course	Classroom training	3 days
46	CBRN Decontamination Course	Classroom training with hands-on exercises	3 or 5 days
47	CBRN Decontamination of Service Animals	Classroom training	No information
48	CBRN Decontamination of Special Groups and Disabled People	Classroom training and practical exercises	3 days
49	Advanced (R&N) Radiation and Nuclear Training Course	Classroom training and practical training	2 weeks

Table 1: Overview of training methods used in international RN-related training courses.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The document provides an overview of altogether 49 RN-related training courses for the international community of first responders, offered by companies and organisations in Austria, Czech Republic, The Netherlands, Qatar, Sweden and by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA; Vienna, Austria). Some these companies cooperate closely in conducting these training courses, e.g., Seibersdorf CBRN Academy, in partnership with CBRN Protection and Hotzone Solution Middle East.

The **content** of these courses ranges from introductory courses lasting from 40 hours, to in-depth training lasting up to six weeks. The courses meet a wide range of **learning objectives**, such as: *Fundamentals of ionizing radiation; Biological and medical effects of radiation; Radiation detection; Radiation protection; Survey; Decontamination; Radiological and nuclear terrorism; Nuclear Emergencies; tasks of the Incident Commander and Emergency Preparedness Coordinator; Response Processes and Capabilities.*

The **didactics** used is mostly traditional classroom lecturing. Only a few courses provide also additional practical training, using equipment and its demonstration. Some offer e-learning, virtual reality and webinars as didactic approach.

The **target audience** addressed by these courses is very wide and encompasses:

- Law enforcement, fire rescue, HAZMAT responders, other public safety officials, and military personnel;
- Scientists, members of the nuclear industry, international organisations, NGO's, and governmental organisations;
- Emergency response personnel and emergency managers;
- Public information, including professionals responsible for communicating with the public and the media, as well as public information officers and emergency preparedness and response experts at local and national levels;
- Specialist teams (such as counterterrorism units, developers of exercise scenarios);
- Medical first responders, emergency medical technicians, ambulance attendants, emergency physicians, nursing staff, support staff and medical administrators, specialists who manage the care for severely exposed or internally contaminated patients;
- Command level responders at border crossings, airports, shipping ports;
- Oil/gas personnel, Cargo companies (air; sea; land).

An important feature of some of these courses is that they tailor the course content to the INDIVIDUAL LEVEL, GROUP LEVEL and COMMAND LEVEL.

In summary, RN-related training courses offered by individual countries and the IAEA for the international community of first responders and emergency managers provide comprehensive training in assessing and managing the consequences of a radiological and nuclear incident. Thereby, they represent a valuable source of practically applicable information for the EU INCLUDING project.